

Pakistan's National Identity Politics in the Late 20th and Early 21st Centuries

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the problems of national identity politics faced during the parliamentary rule of Pakistan in the 1990s. Also, the issue of national identity is revealed in the state political processes of the authoritarian rule of Pervez Musharraf and the democrats who took power in Pakistan after that.*

Keywords: *Pakistan, identity, Benazir Bhutto, Nawaz Sharif, Pervez Musharraf, Zia ul-Haq, ethnopolitics, Islam, regional security.*

Introduction: Military General Zia ul-Haq ruled Pakistan for eleven years (1977-88) and ushered in a period in which religious rule was fully supported as state policy. He made Islamization which was never seen in Pakistan before and since. Anti-regime protest parties, women and human rights defenders were restrained by state security forces and brutally attacked by religious mobs. Television, radio, press, school programs and other institutions promoted Islamic values.

The regime of General Zia-ul-Haq ended in 1988 when he was killed in an air crash. Almost a decade after Zia-ul-Haq came to power, the country has an opportunity to hold democratic elections. Misgovernance, corruption, institutional conflicts, and poor economic management have led to extremely unstable conditions that threaten the survival of fragile democracies. Four elections were held between 1988 and 1999, with control of the government alternating between the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) and the Pakistan Muslim League (PML).

In the "fragile" democratic phase, religious politics were repeatedly used by politicians and parties to strengthen their positions. After the restoration of the parliamentary democratic system in Pakistan, internal political instability and the weakness of the central government were exacerbated by inter-ethnic and inter-religious conflicts. The ruling parties in Pakistan during this period, the PPP and the PML, had clear ethno-regional affiliations, relying on and supporting Sindhis and Punjabis in their politicians, respectively, which in itself constituted a national did not affect the integration.

Main part: The governments of Benazir Bhutto and Nawaz Sharif pursued a dual policy on this issue. On the one hand, in order to maintain internal political stability, they officially demanded an end to violence and called for national unity, while on the other hand, in order to achieve success in the electoral process, the PPP and PML joined both Sunni and Shia religious organizations, in a number of cases their helped by turning a blind eye to his actions.

In 1998, Pakistan's defeat in the "Kargil conflict", which followed the nuclear weapons tests by both India and Pakistan, led to the overthrow of democratic power by Commander-in-Chief Pervez Musharraf.

While summarizing the period of functioning of the party-parliamentary system in Pakistan, ideologically, the political leaders addressed the people as a multi-ethnic, but at the same time ideologically unified union - a single nation. At the same time, politicians emphasized the need to put

an end to the destructive manifestations of authoritarianism in political life and prevent a return to military rule. However, the specific features of the country's constitutional and legal system, namely the inefficient distribution of powers between the president and the prime minister, and the historical participation of the military leadership in the management process, complicated the management process. These problems have led to the instability of civilian governments, which in turn has caused political leaders to fluctuate in their ideological attitudes.

After Perveer Musharraf came to power, he started the "Enlightened Moderation" policy aimed at "getting Pakistanis to abandon militancy and extremism and follow the path of socio-economic development." As for the internal importance of this concept, it included measures aimed at "harmonizing society, curbing inter-communal extremism and promoting religious tolerance." Musharraf's government took measures against terrorist centers on the Pakistan-Afghanistan border, implemented reforms in school curricula, regulated madrasa activities, and liberalized the economy.

In general, the authoritarian regime of Pervez Musharraf and the parliamentary-party governments of Benazir Bhutto and Nawaz Sharif had different political interests as well as different administrative capabilities.

Accordingly, despite the recognition of Pakistan's democratic foundations, opinions about the nature of Pakistan's democracy have been interpreted differently. If the leaders of the PPP and PML parties, who ruled the government in the 1990s, criticized any form of authoritarianism for a liberal society, President Pervez Musharraf, who was a military man by origin, on the contrary, said that building democracy can only be done by an authoritarian regime tried to emphasize.

Asif Ali Zardari and Yusuf Raza Gilani, who came to power after Pervez Musharraf, and during the third Prime Ministership of Nawaz Sharif, like the leaders of Pakistan who ruled the country in the late 20th century and the first decade of the 21st century, Islam was interpreted as the national identity of the state, it was difficult to see support for radical Islam as it had been during the years of Zia ul-Haq's rule.

In them, the main way to achieve national unity was to build democracy, which was reflected in the socio-political ideas of Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the founder of the state. In addition, as in other countries, by this time, politicians using populism began to increase in Pakistan. At the same time, they began to associate populism with Islam. Using the rhetoric of religious populism allows politicians to gain an important position in society and politics. One such politician, Imran Khan's Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf party won the 2018 elections. During the period of Imran Khan, who headed the government from 2018 to 2022, as a result of religious populism, there were cases of distancing from the West in foreign policy, while in domestic policy, the situation of non-Sunni religious groups, especially the Hazaras, became worse.

Conclusion: In national identity, not only language, but also tolerance and mutual acceptance regardless of differences in culture, class and religion are important. Ethnic, cultural, linguistic, religious or sectarian views will never lead to political or economic stability. Among the factors weakening Pakistan's national identity politics was the persistence of prejudice and intolerance based on language, place of origin and sect. For example, Dr. Abdul Qadir Khan, a well-known nuclear scientist and the father of Pakistan's atomic bomb, said in his interview, "When people start identifying themselves not with the country, but with their language, culture, religion, and sect, national integration cannot be expected. This country will never become a united nation by assigning it to linguistic and ethnic units..." he said.

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